

Laser-Induced Cuticle Removal Improves Foliar Zinc Uptake in Row Crops

Authors

Luis Ponce-Cabrera, Teresa Flores-Reyes, Alejandro Ponce-Flores

Onteko Inc., 9924 Alexanders Ridge Dr., Olive Branch, MS, USA 38654

ORCID: Luis Ponce-Cabrera <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3074-0996>; Teresa Flores-Reyes <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0458-2784>; Alejandro Ponce-Flores <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3247-246X>

Corresponding author: luisvponce@ontekollc.com

Abstract

We evaluate a handheld 450 nm continuous-wave laser (FLB-02, Onteko Inc., Olive Branch, MS, USA) to selectively remove epicuticular wax on leaves of zucchini, cowpea, okra, and cotton, and quantify 24-h zinc (Zn) uptake by ICP-OES. Screening identified a forgiving working window at 1.33 m/s (~3–4 W) delivering uniform, non-destructive ablation. Laser-assisted foliar application increased Zn in contralateral leaves across species, consistent with facilitated entry followed by species-dependent redistribution. The results suggest a practical, field-ready approach to enhance foliar nutrient use efficiency.

Keywords

laser; wax cuticle ablation; foliar uptake; zinc; epicuticular wax; precision agriculture

Introduction

Foliar nutrient application faces a fundamental biophysical barrier: the plant cuticle, a composite layer of cutin and epicuticular waxes that restricts the diffusion of water-soluble substances. This hydrophobic layer efficiently minimizes water loss but also limits the uptake efficiency of foliar fertilizers and agrochemicals. Numerous chemical strategies—such as surfactants, adjuvants, chelating agents, and nanoparticle formulations—have been developed to overcome this limitation. However, these approaches often present high cost, environmental persistence, or inconsistent field performance, especially under variable climatic and surface

conditions.

Laser micro-ablation has emerged as a purely physical, non-chemical strategy capable of locally reducing the cuticular barrier without altering the plant's physiology or adding external compounds. Early demonstrations in citrus leaves using CO₂ (10,600 nm), Er:YAG (2,940 nm), and Nd:YAG (532 nm) lasers established the potential of controlled ablation to increase cuticular permeability and enhance foliar uptake of tracers and nutrients [1–3]. Each wavelength interacts differently with the leaf surface, producing distinct effects. The CO₂ laser at 10,600 nm is strongly absorbed by biological tissues and, although effective in removing wax, can be overly aggressive and requires bulky, high-cost equipment not suitable for field use. The Er:YAG laser, operating in the mid-infrared at 2,940 nm, is efficiently absorbed by water and cutin, producing rapid and sometimes explosive exfoliation of the surface layer when pulsed at high fluence. The visible green Nd:YAG laser (532 nm), by contrast, interacts weakly with the wax itself but can promote selective spallation—mechanical lift-off of the wax layer—when operated at sub-thermal fluences, achieving localized and non-destructive ablation.

The blue region of the spectrum, near 450 nm, occupies an intermediate optical domain with unique implications for selective surface processing. While the epicuticular wax layer generally exhibits low absorption in the visible range, several studies indicate a small but measurable absorption tail that extends toward the blue and near-ultraviolet [4, 5]. This partial absorption limits the penetration depth of the beam compared with infrared radiation, confining heat deposition to the outermost micrometers of the surface. Under continuous-wave (CW) operation, such conditions enable gentle photothermal softening and partial melting of the wax film while minimizing the temperature rise in the epidermis and mesophyll. With an appropriate balance of power, scanning speed, and defocus, the wax layer can therefore be selectively removed or redistributed without damaging the underlying tissue.

These optical characteristics make the blue diode laser particularly promising for agricultural applications. In addition to its favorable interaction regime with the wax layer, diode lasers combine compactness, low cost, energy efficiency, and mechanical robustness—qualities that make them uniquely suited for field deployment. Unlike pulsed laboratory systems, they can operate reliably under practical conditions and can be easily integrated into portable or automated devices. This robustness also enables the high productivity required for large-scale or row-crop applications, where thousands of leaves may need to be treated within short timeframes.

Based on these considerations, this study investigates the potential of a 450 nm continuous-wave diode laser to achieve reproducible, non-destructive ablation of epicuticular wax across several representative row crops. We hypothesize that the moderate optical absorption of wax at this wavelength, combined with the limited penetration depth of blue light, creates an effective operational window for selective wax removal while preserving the epidermis. To evaluate this hypothesis, a handheld FLB-02 laser was tested on four morphologically distinct species—zucchini, cowpea, okra, and cotton—covering a range of cuticle thickness and surface microstructures. The experimental objectives were (1) to determine the optimal laser parameters for shallow, uniform ablation without tissue damage; (2) to quantify the resulting enhancement in foliar zinc uptake using independent ICP-OES analysis; and (3) to compare

ablation thresholds and nutrient responses across species. The outcomes aim to establish whether the blue-laser approach can serve as a practical, field-deployable method for selective cuticle removal, supporting the development of laser-assisted foliar fertilization as a scalable, low-cost technology for modern agriculture.

Materials and methods

Plant materials

Greenhouse-grown *Cucurbita pepo* (zucchini), *Vigna unguiculata* (cowpea, cv. black-eyed pea), *Abelmoschus esculentus* (okra), and *Gossypium hirsutum* (cotton) were treated at the 4–6-leaf stage. A total of 40 plants per crop were used: 20 controls (Zn only) and 20 laser + Zn, arranged as matched pairs by species and stage.

Laser device and treatment geometry

A handheld 450 nm continuous-wave diode laser (**FLB-02**, Onteko Inc., Olive Branch, MS, USA) was used. The system delivered 2.0–5.0 W at the workplane (verified with a calibrated powermeter), with ~ 75 μm at slight defocus (~ 7 mm) and a galvanometer raster to generate three $\sim 20 \times 5$ mm swaths per leaf at 1.33 m/s unless otherwise noted.

Parameter screening and working windows

Two user variables controlled the delivered laser dose: power (W) and scanning speed (m/s). Preliminary trials were carried out to establish the operational range capable of removing the epicuticular wax layer without producing visible thermal injury to the epidermis. For each crop, sacrificial leaves were first used to explore the speed window at constant power (4.955 W nominal). The resulting laser swaths were classified under a digital microscope as shallow, optimal, or excessive according to their visual and textural characteristics.

Figure 1 shows the working domain at 1.14 m/s; Figure 2 shows 1.33 m/s. Comparing both, the safe operating window broadens at 1.33 m/s. At the lower speed, the laser dwell time increased, producing a narrower safe range and a rapid shift from optimal to excessive ablation. Several species—particularly okra and zucchini—showed localized epidermal browning or gloss changes near the lower-speed edge, indicating heat accumulation and reduced thermal tolerance. In contrast, at 1.33 m/s, the ablation regime expanded significantly: the shallow–optimal and optimal–excessive boundaries became well separated, and the treated zones appeared uniformly matte, lightened, and free of perforation or carbonization across all crops. This wider plateau of stable operation suggests an improved balance between surface energy input and heat dissipation within the wax film.

Based on these results, 1.33 m/s was selected as the standard scanning velocity for subsequent power-sweep experiments. Operating at this speed provided consistent and reproducible

ablation morphology across zucchini, cowpea, okra, and cotton, confirming that the blue diode laser primarily softens and redistributes the epicuticular wax through controlled photothermal action. The corresponding power working windows at this velocity are shown in Figure 2, where each crop exhibits a distinct but overlapping optimal band centered between 3.0 and 4.0 W, well below the damage threshold. The quantitative summary of these thresholds is provided in Table 1, which lists, for each species, the ablation onset, applied working power, and the absence of detectable epidermal injury up to the highest tested values.

Together, Figures 1–2 and Table 1 demonstrate that 1.33 m/s represents the center of a broad, multi-species operational window that ensures uniform ablation, high repeatability, and safe epidermal preservation—conditions essential for field-ready implementation of laser-assisted foliar treatments.

Figure 1. Power working windows for zucchini, cowpea, okra, and cotton at a scanning velocity of 1.14 m/s.

Figure 2. Power working windows for zucchini, cowpea, okra, and cotton at a scanning velocity of 1.33 m/s.

Table 1. Laser power parameters and damage thresholds for four crop species.

Crop	Speed (m/s)	Ablation threshold (W)	Applied power (W)	Damage threshold (W)
Zucchini	1.33	2.0	4.0	Not reached
Cowpea	1.33	1.5	4.0	Not reached
Okra	1.33	2.5	4.0	Not reached
Cotton	1.33	2.5	4.0	Not reached

Foliar Zn application

A chelated Zn fertilizer (Opulent Zn, 23% w/v) served as the tracer. The commercial concentrate was diluted in deionized water according to the manufacturer's foliar-use instructions (10 mL L⁻¹) to obtain the working solution. Immediately after laser treatment, 30 µL of this diluted solution was pipetted onto the treated region of each leaf, ensuring full coverage of the ablated area. Control plants received the same droplet volume and concentration on the corresponding position without laser exposure.

Sampling and analysis

At 24 hours after treatment, tissue was collected from the contralateral (opposite) leaves of each plant to assess Zn distribution away from the treated site. Two leaves per plant were combined to obtain approximately 500 g fresh mass, as required by the analytical laboratory. Samples were refrigerated immediately and cold-shipped to Waypoint Analytical Tennessee, Inc., which performed plant tissue analysis by ICP-OES according to its standard procedures. Reported values represent total Zn concentration expressed in ppm on a dry-weight basis.

Data handling and statistics

For each crop, the analyzed sample represented a pooled composite of leaves collected from multiple plants within the same treatment group (laser-treated or control). Because pooling integrates biological variability at the sampling stage, each analytical result reflects a single composite value per treatment and species, rather than independent plant-level observations. As a result, plant-level dispersion metrics (e.g., SD) and significance testing (e.g., t-tests) cannot be computed from the present design. Results are therefore reported as absolute Zn concentrations (ppm, dry weight) and as relative increases (%) of laser-treated samples with respect to their corresponding controls. Future experiments will include biological replicates ($n \geq 3$) per treatment and species to quantify variability and enable statistical testing.

Results

Laser ablation outcomes

Mechanistically, prior citrus studies identified regimes consistent with selective spallation at 532 nm (pulsed Nd:YAG) and selective exfoliation at 2940 nm (Er:YAG) [2,3]. In contrast, at 450 nm continuous wave with slight defocus, the response observed here is dose-governed and photothermal. In the slower regimen (Figure 1, 1.14 m/s), three of the four crops show shallow outcomes at 1.5–2.0 W, an optimal band from 2.5 to 4.0 W, and excessive effects at ≥ 4.5 W. Moving to the faster regimen (Figure 2) broadens the safe operating window for every species: shallow persists up to 2.5 W, while the optimal regime extends from 3.0 W to at least 4.95 W, with no “excessive” zone observed within the tested range. These results justify selecting 1.33 m/s for subsequent treatments, as it provides a consistently wider optimal band and greater safety margin across crops; Table 1 lists the working values used within that band.

Morphology of treated areas

With a scanning velocity of 1.33 m/s, laser intensity adjusted near each crop’s optimal range, a single raster pass, and approximately 7 mm defocus, the treated swaths appeared dull-matte and uniformly lightened, with no perforations or carbonization. This morphology is consistent

with selective removal or redistribution of the epicuticular wax layer while preserving the integrity of the underlying epidermal tissue.

Figure 3: Representative microscope images of laser-treated zones on zucchini, cowpea, okra, and cotton (left to right). Laser power: 4.0 W; speed: 1.33 m/s; single pass; ~7 mm defocus.

Zinc uptake enhancement

ICP-OES analysis showed higher Zn concentrations in all four laser-treated crops compared with their corresponding Zn-only controls. The relative ranking was consistent across species: zucchini $\approx 2\times$, cowpea and okra $\sim 1.5\text{--}1.8\times$, and cotton $\sim 1.2\text{--}1.4\times$ higher than control values (see Figure 4). Because sampling targeted contralateral leaves approximately 24 hours after treatment, these increases reflect systemic redistribution of zinc following its facilitated entry at the laser-treated sites. The magnitude of response varied mainly among species, consistent with differences in leaf structure, cuticle composition, and phloem mobility, which govern the efficiency of post-entry zinc transport [4,5].

Figure 4. Normalized zinc (Zn) content across crops at 24 h. Values are relative to the untreated control (set at 100%).

Discussion

Cross-species efficacy

Selective cuticle ablation at 450 nm increased Zn measured in contralateral leaves at 24 h for all four species (Figure 4). Species-to-species variability tracks leaf surface traits (wax amount/chemistry, trichomes, micro-relief), lamina thickness/hydration, and the efficiency of short-term phloem loading. Cowpea showed the lowest ablation threshold (~ 1.5 W) yet a clear 24-h contralateral increase, consistent with facile entry once the cuticle is locally opened (Table 1). Zucchini exhibited the largest proportional gain, which matches expectations for a highly hydrophobic, wax-rich surface once breached. In contrast, okra and cotton displayed smaller relative increases despite similar safe working powers ($\sim 3\text{--}4$ W at 1.33 m/s) this is plausibly explained by species-dependent post-entry transport, as Zn phloem mobility and redistribution can be limited and strongly context-dependent, particularly in crops with thicker cuticles and robust near-surface heat sinking that require slightly higher ablation onset (2.5 W for okra and cotton) (Table 1). Importantly, these outcomes align with prior principles: opening the cuticle enhances foliar entry, whereas onward transport depends on species physiology and loading pathways. Future work should explicitly quantify phloem mobility in cotton/okra (e.g., radiotracers or μ -XRF time-series) to separate entry from redistribution [1-3, 5].

Mechanistic considerations

Unlike pulsed 532 nm or Er:YAG regimes, the 450 nm CW method relies on a dose-governed photothermal mechanism: with slight defocus and a single raster pass, epicuticular wax is preferentially softened/mobilized while epidermal cells remain viable, yielding microscale high-permeability windows. The clustered ablation onsets of $\sim 1.5\text{--}2.5$ W across species—with safe working powers typically $\sim 3\text{--}4$ W at the reference speed—support a common, dose-controlled surface mechanism rather than species-specific spectral resonances (Figure 1, Table 1). Blue-region absorption by photosynthetic pigments contributes to the near-surface heating profile that enables selectivity when dwell and total dose are appropriately tuned [6].

Practical advantages

A compact, air-cooled handheld unit enables field readiness; galvanometer rastering provides repeatable geometry with partial-area coverage sufficient for strong effects; and, at the reference speed, we observed no epidermal damage within the tested power range (≤ 4.95 W), indicating a generous operational margin.

Although wavelengths and delivery modes differ, all successful approaches share the principle of transiently lowering cuticular resistance to enhance infiltration and downstream transport. At 532 nm (pulsed Nd:YAG) the effect is selective wax ablation [2,3]; 2940 nm (Er:YAG) produces cuticle exfoliation over the illuminated spot [2,3]; and the present 450 nm continuous-wave

raster traces centimeter-scale paths composed of multiple parallel lines, each tens of micrometers in diameter. This geometry covers large areas efficiently (via high scan speed and dense line packing) while perturbing only a small fraction of the surface at any instant—features that may facilitate wax-cuticle recovery (future work). Even with partial coverage, we observed meaningful 24-h Zn increases (Figure 4), indicating that strategically placed high-permeability windows are sufficient; full-leaf coverage is unnecessary.

Conclusions

A handheld 450 nm CW laser (FLB-02, Onteko) reliably produces selective, superficial cuticle removal in multiple row crops within a forgiving operating window. Across zucchini, cowpea, okra, and cotton, a reference regimen at 1.33 m/s with powers in the ~3.0–4.0 W band yielded uniform, matte swaths without carbonization or perforation, consistent with wax removal while preserving epidermal viability. Despite treating only a small fraction of the leaf area (~3.0 cm²) and applying a minimal Zn dose (30 µL), we observed measurable 24-h Zn increases in contralateral leaves, indicating that strategically placed high-permeability windows can suffice to enhance entry and early redistribution—full-leaf coverage is unnecessary.

Operationally, the approach is portable, repeatable, and energy-controlled; the separation between shallow–optimal and optimal–excessive regimes at 1.33 m/s offers a wide safety margin for routine use. Taken together with prior citrus work, these findings support laser-assisted foliar feeding as a practical precision-agriculture tool to (i) improve nutrient-use efficiency with lower spray volumes, (ii) reduce runoff and off-target deposition, and (iii) enable site-specific dosing on high-value leaves or canopy sectors.

Scope and generality. Although demonstrated here with Zn, the mechanism—transient reduction of cuticular resistance—should generalize to other mobile nutrients (e.g., Fe, Mn, B), especially when paired with micro-sprayers to standardize application at the treated swath.

The FLB-02 workflow integrates with existing greenhouse/field practices (simple alignment, single pass, brief spray), and its parameter window is sufficiently broad to support operator training and SOPs for research and early field validation.

With modest hardware and clear SOPs, laser-assisted foliar feeding can evolve from research use to deployable practice that uses less product for the same (or better) plant uptake, offering agronomic, environmental, and economic upside.

Limitations and next steps

This study reports pooled composites at a single 24-h endpoint and focuses on Zn across four species; plant-level dispersion and time-course kinetics were not quantified. Next, we will (i) run biological replicates ($n \geq 3$) per species to enable statistics, (ii) expand to multi-time-point ICP and mobility mapping (e.g., μ -XRF or radiotracers) to separate entry vs. redistribution, (iii) test additional nutrients/formulations, and (iv) scale from handheld to gantry/sprayer-mounted delivery to evaluate operational throughput, input savings, and yield/quality outcomes under randomized field trials.

Funding

This work received support from Innovate Mississippi (Grant Innovate MS).

Acknowledgments

We thank Innovate Mississippi, AgLaunch, and the I-Corps University of Memphis Hub for their guidance and support. We also acknowledge Waypoint Analytical Tennessee, Inc. for ICP-OES analyses.

Conflicts of Interest

Onteko Inc. owns the intellectual property covering the laser-assisted foliar uptake technology reported here (patent pending; including US Patent Application No. 18/450,483). The authors are affiliated with Onteko Inc. No other competing interests are declared.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization: LPC; Methodology: LPC; Investigation: LPC, TFR; Data curation: LPC, APF; Visualization: LPC, APF; Writing – original draft: LPC; Writing – review & editing: LPC and co-authors.

References

1. Etxeberria, E., Gonzalez, P., Fanton Borges, A., & Brodersen, C. (2016). The use of laser light to enhance the uptake of foliar-applied substances into citrus (*Citrus sinensis*) leaves. *Applications in Plant Sciences*, 4, 1500106. <https://doi.org/10.3732/apps.1500106>
2. Ponce-Cabrera, L., Etxeberria, E., Gonzalez, P., & Flores-Reyes, T. (2023). Use of non-intrusive laser exfoliation to improve substance uptake into citrus leaves. *F1000Research*, 12, 303. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.129789.1>
3. Ponce-Cabrera, L., Ponce-Flores, A., Flores-Reyes, T., & Ponce-Flores, E. (2025). Selective wax cuticle removal using green wavelength lasers: A non-invasive method for

- enhancing foliar uptake. *AgriEngineering*, 7(4), 119.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/agriengineering7040119>
4. Riederer, M., & Schreiber, L. (2001). Protecting against water loss: Analysis of the barrier properties of plant cuticles. *Journal of Experimental Botany*, 52(363), 2023–2032.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/jexbot/52.363.2023>
 5. Fernández, V., & Eichert, T. (2009). Uptake of hydrophilic solutes through plant leaves: Current state of knowledge and perspectives of foliar fertilization. *Critical Reviews in Plant Sciences*, 28(1), 36–68. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07352680902743069>
 6. Ptushenko, O. S., Ptushenko, V. V., & Solovchenko, A. E. (2020). Spectrum of light as a determinant of plant functioning: A historical perspective. *Life*, 10(3), 25.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/life10030025>